

Interview grid

Introduction

1. Please recall the moment, when it became obvious that kindergartens and schools were going to be closed due to the outbreak of the virus, and tell us about the first weekend what were you thinking – alone or together with your husband / partner – about how you would deal with work and family in the next few weeks, how did you imagine this period? *(if she needs help with what to mention: what plans did they have for the organization of work, what solutions they came up with regarding the children; what seemed to be the most difficult issue and what solution they had for that)*
2. Now, I would ask you to tell me what it has been like: how have you been living since 16th March? (again, if she is clueless: what does she consider to be the most important about their daily lives)

From now on, after the two longer reports, I consider the following questions more as a kind of checklist. Asking any of the questions, we can relate to the “main narratives”: “you mentioned earlier, that ...”

Childcare, motherhood

- Please, tell us, how your average (weekday) day looks like at the moment!
- Please, tell us, how your kindergarten and school solves online learning!
- Who supervises the child, from when till when? Are there rules for it or is it spontaneous? Is there a change in the habits compared to pre-lock-down?
- Overall, how do you evaluate these days in terms of scheduling and task allocation?
- Within the present circumstances, can you rely on anyone in taking care of the children: babysitter, grandparent, another family, children of another family, the wider family, etc.?
- Is your life very different now than it was before quarantine?
- How have children's habits of watching TV, using the computer and/or the mobile phone changed as a result of the lock-down? How do you feel about this? What aspects do you consider in this question? Has your opinion on it changed since the lock-down?

Household and elderly care tasks and their distribution

- How are the household tasks distributed? Has it changed since pre-lock-down? (E.g., washing, cooking, cleaning, shopping, repairing; separately: logistics, organization: keep in mind what to buy, shop for ingredients)
- Do you have to take care of an elderly or sick person, if so, how do you manage it? What are the tasks that they need help with?
- Have you been able to involve outside help in the field of domestic work and care for the elderly since the lock-down: who, how many times, for what tasks, for what reasons, what do you think about this decision?
- How satisfied are you with this schedule and task allocation?

Work organization, work and family reconciliation

- Please, tell us, how you work before the lock-down and how your work changed during the lock-down period! (exact position, responsibilities, job field, length of working hours, flexibility-constrained: this includes workplace flexibility as well, if relevant: how creative the job is, how much autonomy she has)
- Please, tell us, how your husband worked before the lock-down and how his work changed during the lock-down period! (exact position, responsibilities, job field, length of working hours, flexibility-constrained: this includes workplace flexibility as well, if relevant: how creative the job is, how much autonomy he has)
- Is there a change in how well you can concentrate on your work? Do you work with background noise? How do you “turn it off”? Can you retreat, and what happens with the rest of the family in the meantime? Can you help each other with your husband in this?
- How does this work, how satisfied are you with this situation? How do you feel, is work and private life in balance?
- Does the epidemic or crisis affect the job security or wage level of either of you?

Mental health

Relations, support, solidarity

- Let’s leave now the organization of daily life, and talk about mental support. Have you been able to keep in touch with the most important people? Please, tell me more about it!
- Is there a person in your environment who relies on you (too) mentally, to whom it is important to stay in touch with you? Were you able to keep in touch with that/those person(s)?
- Can you talk with your husband, do you have time and opportunity for that, are you satisfied with that?

Optional auxiliary questions: What do you think, how are others struggling with this situation, how are they doing, what strategies do they use? What do you think to be good and less good among those?

Summary

- Overall, how did you experience the last few weeks during the lock-down?
- Please, say 2-3 positive and negative things about it. Is there something (habit, practice) you would like to keep in the future?